
BUILDING THE EOSC OPEN SCIENCE OBSERVATORY

Analysis of Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2024

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	1
1. Introduction.....	3
2. Publications.....	6
2.1. Policies.....	6
2.1.1. National Policies on Publications.....	6
2.1.2. Financial Strategy on Publications.....	9
2.2. Practices.....	10
2.2.1. National Monitoring on Publications.....	10
2.2.2. National Investments in Publications.....	11
2.3. Impacts.....	12
2.3.1. Progress in Policies on Publications.....	12
2.3.2. Progress in Practices on Publications.....	15
3. Data.....	16
3.1. Policies.....	16
3.1.1. National Policies on Data.....	16
3.1.2. Financial Strategies on Data.....	18
3.2. Practices.....	21
3.2.1. National Monitoring on Data.....	21
3.2.2. National Investments in Data.....	24
3.3. Impacts.....	26
3.3.1. Progress in Policies on Data.....	26
3.3.2. Progress in Practices on Data.....	29
4. Software.....	33
4.1. Policies.....	33
4.1.1. National Policy on Software.....	33
4.1.2. Financial Strategy on Software.....	34
4.2. Practices.....	34
4.2.1. National Monitoring on Software.....	34
4.2.2. National Investments in Software.....	35
4.3. Impacts.....	35
4.3.1. Progress in Policies on Software.....	35
4.3.2. Progress in Practices on Software.....	36
5. Services.....	38
5.1. Policies.....	38
5.1.1. National Policy on Services.....	38
5.1.2. Financial Strategy on Services.....	39

5.2.	Practices.....	40
5.2.1.	National Monitoring on Services.....	40
5.2.2.	National Investments in Services.....	41
5.3.	Impacts.....	42
5.3.1.	Progress in Policies on Services.....	42
5.3.2.	Progress in Practices on Services.....	43
6.	Infrastructure.....	45
6.1.	Policies.....	45
6.1.1.	National Policies on Infrastructure.....	45
6.1.2.	Financial Strategies on Infrastructure.....	48
6.2.	Practices.....	51
6.2.1.	National Monitoring on Infrastructure.....	51
6.2.2.	National Investments in Infrastructure.....	54
6.3.	Impacts.....	56
6.3.1.	Progress in Policies on Infrastructure.....	56
6.3.2.	Progress in Practices on Infrastructure.....	59
7.	Skills/Training.....	63
7.1.	Policies.....	63
7.1.1.	National Policy on Skills/Training.....	63
7.1.2.	Financial Strategy on Skills/Training.....	64
7.2.	Practices.....	64
7.2.1.	National Monitoring on Skills/Training.....	64
7.2.2.	National Investments in Skills/Training.....	65
7.3.	Impacts.....	66
7.3.1.	Progress in Policies on Skills/Training.....	66
7.3.2.	Progress in Practices on Skills/Training.....	67
8.	Assessment.....	69
8.1.	Policies.....	69
8.1.1.	National Policy on Assessment.....	69
8.1.2.	Financial Strategy on Assessment.....	70
8.2.	Practices.....	70
8.2.1.	National Monitoring on Assessment.....	70
8.2.2.	National Investments in Assessment.....	71
8.3.	Impacts.....	72
8.3.1.	Progress in Policies on Assessment.....	72
8.3.2.	Progress in Practices on Assessment.....	73
9.	Engagement.....	75
9.1.	Policies.....	75

9.1.1.	National Policy on Engagement.....	75
9.1.2.	Financial Strategy on Engagement.....	76
9.2.	Practices.....	76
9.2.1.	National Monitoring on Engagement.....	76
9.2.2.	National Investments in Engagement.....	77
9.3.	Impacts.....	78
9.3.1.	Progress in Policies on Engagement.....	78
9.3.2.	Progress in Practices on Engagement.....	79
10.	Total Investments in EOSC and Open Science.....	81
10.1.	Total Investments in Millions of Euros.....	81
10.2.	Total Investments per 1000 FTE Researchers.....	81
	References.....	83

Executive Summary

This report offers an Analysis of the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2024. Survey 2024 was published in the EOSC Open Science Observatory on 21 February 2025 and ran until 29 August 2025 whereby 31 countries responded consisting of 24 of the 27 European Union (EU) countries and 7 non-EU countries. The annual survey is targeted at the national members of the EOSC Steering Board and monitors relevant policy, practice, and impact indicators related to EOSC and Open Science at national and institutional levels in Europe. The report is structured around the eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science and presents survey results for publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement as well as for total investments in EOSC and Open Science. The report focuses on the policies, financial strategies, monitoring, investments, and progress across the EU-27 countries for each of the categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science.

Selected highlights from the results of Survey 2024 for responding EU-27 countries are presented below:

- **Publications:** The countries are prioritising research publications as 92% (22/24) have a national policy (whereby 41% (9/22) are mandatory), 52% (12/23) have a financial strategy, and 65% (15/23) have a national monitoring on open access to publications. Furthermore, 68% (15/22) have a specific policy on immediate open access to publications (whereby 47% (7/15) are mandatory), 65% (13/20) have a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications (whereby 54% (7/13) are mandatory), and 64% (14/22) have a specific policy on open licensing of publications (whereby 29% (4/14) are mandatory).
- **Data:** Countries are also prioritising research data as 79% (19/24) have a national policy (whereby 53% (10/19) are mandatory), 48% (11/23) have a financial strategy, and 14% (3/22) have a national monitoring on data management. Secondly, 71% (17/24) have a national policy (whereby 35% (6/17) are mandatory), 46% (11/24) have a financial strategy, and 13% (3/23) have a national monitoring on FAIR data. Lastly, 83% (20/24) have a national policy (whereby 58% (11/19) are mandatory), 43% (10/23) have a financial strategy, and 40% (8/20) have a national monitoring on open data.
- **Software:** There is less of a national focus on research software as 38% (9/24) of the countries have a national policy (whereby 22% (2/9) are mandatory), 0% (0/24) have a financial strategy, and 14% (3/22) have a national monitoring on open-source software.
- **Skills/Training:** Countries show moderate interest in research skills/training as 65% (15/23) have a national policy (whereby 7% (1/15) are mandatory), 35% (8/23) have a financial strategy, and 17% (4/23) have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science.

- Assessment: The same applies for research assessment as 52% (12/23) of countries have a national policy (whereby 33% (4/12) are mandatory), 30% (7/23) have a financial strategy, and 14% (3/22) have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science.
- Engagement: Countries are again moderately focused on engaging citizens in research as 50% (12/24) have a national policy (whereby 17% (2/12) are mandatory), 17% (4/24) have a financial strategy, and 13% (3/23) have a national monitoring on citizen science.
- Investments: The countries are making substantial financial investments as 4% (1/24) invested >0 to 1 €M, 25% (6/24) invested >1 to 5 €M, 25% (6/24) invested >10 to 50 €M, and 8% (2/24) invested >50 to 100 €M in EOSC and Open Science in 2023. When comparing the countries in terms of their researcher populations, we see that 8% (2/24) invested >0 to 50 €K, 13% (3/24) invested >50 to 100 €K, 25% (6/24) invested >100 to 250 €K, 4% (1/24) invested >250 to 500 €K, 8% (2/24) invested >500 to 1000 €K, and 4% (1/24) invested >1000 €K in EOSC and Open Science per 1000 FTE researchers.

1. Introduction

This report offers an Analysis of the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2024. The survey was developed by the EOSC Future project [1] and EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) [2] to monitor policies, practices, and impacts related to EOSC and Open Science at national and institutional levels in Europe. The survey is targeted at the national members of EOSC-SB and runs annually, whereby a pilot survey was conducted in 2021 [3] and the first full survey was conducted in 2022 [4]. The results of each annual survey are archived in the EOSC Observatory Zenodo Community [5] and exploitable in the EOSC Open Science Observatory [6] which was first developed in EOSC Future and continued in the EOSC Track project [7].

The survey for 2024 is based on the revised version of the Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC [8] which consists of indicators for policies, practices, and impact across eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science including publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement as shown in Table 1. This report provides an analysis of responses related to two policy indicators of countries with a national policy and financial strategy, two practice indicators of countries with a national monitoring and investments, and one impact indicator on yearly progress in policies and practices. Each analysis is supported by graphs which focus on positive responses, whereby negative responses group countries which either responded negatively to a question or did not respond to a question.

	Policies	Practices	Impacts
Publications	Countries with a National Policy	Countries with National Monitoring	Country Impact Stories
Data			
Software	Countries with a Financial Strategy	Country Use Cases	Country Output Outcomes
Services			
Infrastructure	Country RPOs with a Policy	Country Investments	Correlation between Country Indicators
Skills/Training			
Assessment	Country RFOs with a Policy	Country Outputs	Yearly Progress in Country Indicators

Table 1: Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC

Survey 2024 [9] was published in the EOSC Open Science Observatory on 21 February 2025 and ran until 29 August 2025, whereby 31 countries responded consisting of 24 of the 27 European Union (EU) countries and 7 non-EU countries as shown in Tables 2 and 3. This report is based on the data collected from Survey 2024 [10] and focuses exclusively on the survey results for the 24 responding EU countries. It should be noted that only one response is accepted from Belgium, whereby an answer is marked positive if there is a policy, financial

strategy, or national monitoring in at least one region or community or at the federal level, and whereby investments are calculated at the federal level. It should also be noted that all responses and investments from Germany are at the federal level.

Group	Country	Survey 2022	Survey 2023	Survey 2024
EU (27)	Austria	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Belgium	No	Yes	Yes
	Denmark	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Finland	Yes	Yes	Yes
	France	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Germany	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Italy	No	Yes	Yes
	Luxembourg	Yes	Yes	No
	Netherlands	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Republic of Ireland	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Spain	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Sweden	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Bulgaria	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Croatia	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Cyprus	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Czech Republic	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Estonia	Yes	No	Yes
	Greece	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Hungary	Yes	No	Yes
	Latvia	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Lithuania	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Malta	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Poland	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Portugal	Yes	Yes	No
	Romania	No	No	No
	Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Slovenia	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 2: EU Countries Responding to Survey 2022 to Survey 2024

Group	Country	Survey 2022	Survey 2023	Survey 2024
Non-EU	Armenia	Yes	Yes	No
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Yes	No	No
	Faroe Islands	No	Yes	Yes
	Georgia	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Iceland	No	No	Yes
	Norway	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Serbia	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Switzerland	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Turkey	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Ukraine	Yes	No	No
	United Kingdom	No	Yes	No

Table 3: Non-EU Countries Responding to Survey 2022 to Survey 2024

The report is structured around the eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science and presents survey results for publications (Section 2), data (Section 3), software (Section 4), services (Section 5), infrastructure (Section 6), skills/training (Section 7), assessment (Section 8), and engagement (Section 9) as well as for total investments in EOSC and Open Science (Section 10).

2. Publications

2.1. Policies

2.1.1. National Policies on Publications

The first main policy question on open access to publications in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on open access to publications?* (Q1) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.1). A policy hereby refers to any policies, recommendations, regulations, or laws which are relevant for EOSC and Open Science, and which are applicable at national or regional levels. 92% (22/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open access to publications, whereby 41% (9/22) are mandatory as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

Figure 2: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

One sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on immediate open access to publications?* (Q1.3) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.3.1). 68% (15/22) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on immediate open access to publications, whereby 47% (7/15) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3: Map of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

Figure 4: Share of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

Another sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on retention of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) on publications?* (Q1.4) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.4.1). 65% (13/20) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications, whereby 54% (7/13) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Map of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

Figure 6: Share of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

A final sub-question related to having a national policy on open access to publications is *Is there a specific policy on open licensing of publications?* (Q1.5) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q1.5.1). 64% (14/22) of responding EU countries have a specific policy on open licensing of publications, whereby 29% (4/14) of those policies are mandatory as shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7: Map of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

Figure 8: Share of EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

2.1.2. Financial Strategy on Publications

The second main policy question on open access to publications in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open access to publications?* (Q2). A financial strategy hereby refers to any self-standing strategy or strategy which is included in an overarching strategy at national or regional levels. 52% (12/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on open access to publications as shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

Figure 10: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

2.2. Practices

2.2.1. National Monitoring on Publications

The first main practice question on open access to publications in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open access to publications?* (Q49). National monitoring hereby refers to any monitoring of policies or practices at national or regional levels. 65% (15/23) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open access to publications as shown in Figures 11 and 12.

Figure 11: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

Figure 12: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

2.2.2. National Investments in Publications

The second main practice question on open access to publications in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in open access to publications in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q51). 38% (9/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in open access to publications. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 13% (3/24) >50 to 100 €K, 25% (6/24) >100 to 250 €K, 13% (3/24) >250 to 500 €K, 4% (1/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Open Access to Publications per 1000 FTE Researchers

2.3. Impacts

2.3.1. Progress in Policies on Publications

There is an increase in national policies on open access to publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Access to Publications

There is an increase in specific policies on immediate open access to publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Progress in EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Immediate Open Access to Publications

There is an increase in specific policies on retention of IPR on publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Progress in EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Retention of IPR on Publications

There is an increase in specific policies on open licensing of publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is no change in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Progress in EU Countries with a Specific Policy on Open Licensing of Publications

There is a decrease in financial strategies on open access to publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Access to Publications

2.3.2. Progress in Practices on Publications

There is an increase in national monitoring on open access to publications in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Access to Publications

There is an increase in national investments in open access to publications per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Open Access to Publications per 1000 FTE Researchers

3. Data

The data category consists of three main topics: data management, FAIR data [11], and open data.

3.1. Policies

3.1.1. National Policies on Data

The first main policy question on data management in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on data management?* (Q5) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q5.1). 79% (19/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on data management, whereby 53% (10/19) are mandatory as shown in Figures 21 and 22.

Figure 21: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

Figure 22: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

The first main policy question on FAIR data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on FAIR data?* (Q9) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q9.1). 71% (17/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on FAIR data, whereby 35% (6/17) are mandatory as shown in Figures 23 and 24.

Figure 23: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

Figure 24: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

The first main policy question on open data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on open data?* (Q13) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q13.1). 83% (20/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open data, whereby 58% (11/19) are mandatory as shown in Figures 25 and 26.

Figure 25: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

Figure 26: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

3.1.2. Financial Strategies on Data

The second main policy question on data management in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on data management?* (Q6). 48% (11/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on data management as shown in Figures 27 and 28.

Figure 27: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

Figure 28: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

The second main policy question on FAIR data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on FAIR data?* (Q10). 46% (11/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on FAIR data as shown in Figures 29 and 30.

Figure 29: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

Figure 30: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

The second main policy question on open data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open data?* (Q14). 43% (10/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on open data as shown in Figures 31 and 32.

Figure 31: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

Figure 32: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

3.2. Practices

3.2.1. National Monitoring on Data

The first main practice question in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on data management?* (Q53). 14% (3/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on data management as shown in Figures 33 and 34.

Figure 33: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

Figure 34: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

The first main practice question on FAIR data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on FAIR data?* (Q57). 13% (3/23) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on FAIR data as shown in Figures 35 and 36.

Figure 35: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

Figure 36: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

The first main practice question on open data in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open data?* (Q61). 40% (8/20) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open data as shown in Figures 37 and 38.

Figure 37: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

Figure 38: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

3.2.2. National Investments in Data

The second main practice question on data management in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in data management in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q55). 75% (18/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in data management. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 8% (2/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Data Management per 1000 FTE Researchers

The second main practice question on FAIR data in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in FAIR data in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q59). 92% (22/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in FAIR data. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 0% (0/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in FAIR Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

The second main practice question on open data in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in open data in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q63). 83% (20/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in open data. 4% (1/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) >50 to 100 €K, 4% (1/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 4% (1/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Open Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

3.3. Impacts

3.3.1. Progress in Policies on Data

There is an increase in national policies on data management in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, as shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Management

There is an increase in national policies on FAIR data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 43.

Figure 43: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on FAIR Data

There is an increase in national policies on open data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Open Data

There is no change in financial strategies on data management in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 45.

Figure 45: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Management

There is a decrease in financial strategies on FAIR data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on FAIR Data

There is an increase in financial strategies on open data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 47.

Figure 47: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open Data

3.3.2. Progress in Practices on Data

There has been no change in national monitoring on data management in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and overall no change since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 48.

Figure 48: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Management

There is an increase in national monitoring on FAIR data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on FAIR Data

There is an increase in national monitoring on open data in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open Data

There is a decrease in national investments in data management per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 51.

Figure 51: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Data Management per 1000 FTE Researchers

There is an increase in national investments in FAIR data per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 52.

Figure 52: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in FAIR Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

There is an increase in national investments in open data per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Open Data per 1000 FTE Researchers

4. Software

The software category consists of one main topic: open-source software.

4.1. Policies

4.1.1. National Policy on Software

The first main policy question on open-source software in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on open-source software?* (Q17) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q17.1). 38% (9/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on open-source software whereby 22% (2/9) are mandatory as shown in Figures 54 and 55.

Figure 54: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open-Source Software

Figure 55: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Open-Source Software

4.1.2. Financial Strategy on Software

The second main policy question on open-source software in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on open-source software?* (Q18). 0% (0/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on open-source software.

4.2. Practices

4.2.1. National Monitoring on Software

The first main practice question on open-source software in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on open-source software?* (Q65). 14% (3/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on open-source software as shown in Figures 56 and 57.

Figure 56: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open-Source Software

Figure 57: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open-Source Software

4.2.2. National Investments in Software

The second main practice question on open-source software in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in open-source software in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q67). 75% (18/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in open-source software. 21% (5/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 58.

Figure 58: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Open-Source Software per 1000 FTE Researchers

4.3. Impacts

4.3.1. Progress in Policies on Software

There is an increase in national policies on open-source software in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Open-Source Software

There is no change in financial strategies on open-source software in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and overall no change since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Open-Source Software

4.3.2. Progress in Practices on Software

There is an increase in national monitoring on open-source software in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 61.

Figure 61: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Open-Source Software

There is an increase in national investments in open-source software per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 62.

Figure 62: Trend in EU Countries with National Investments in Open-Source Software per 1000 FTE Researchers

5. Services

The services category consists of one main topic: offering services through EOSC.

5.1. Policies

5.1.1. National Policy on Services

The first main policy question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on offering services through EOSC?* (Q21) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q21.1). Offering services through EOSC hereby refers to ensuring that research services are made available in EOSC-Exchange [12] to serve the needs of researchers and research communities. We note that this definition will likely change in future surveys as the concepts of EOSC-Core [13] and EOSC-Exchange have in the meantime been replaced by the EOSC EU Node [14] and future contributions to EOSC are foreseen by enrolling an EOSC Node into the EOSC Federation or by onboarding resources to an EOSC Node. 29% (7/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on offering services through EOSC, whereby 29% (2/7) are mandatory as shown in Figures 63 and 64.

Figure 63: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

Figure 64: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOOSC

5.1.2. Financial Strategy on Services

The second main policy question on offering services through EOOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on offering services through EOOSC?* (Q22). 21% (5/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on offering services through EOOSC as shown in Figures 65 and 66.

Figure 65: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOOSC

Figure 66: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

5.2. Practices

5.2.1. National Monitoring on Services

The first main practice question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on offering services through EOSC?* (Q69). 5% (1/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on offering services through EOSC as shown in Figures 67 and 68.

Figure 67: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOSC

Figure 68: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOSC

5.2.2. National Investments in Services

The second main practice question on offering services through EOSC in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in offering services through EOSC in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q71). 92% (22/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in offering services through EOSC. 4% (1/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) >50 to 100 €K 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 69.

Figure 69: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

5.3. Impacts

5.3.1. Progress in Policies on Services

There is an increase in national policies on offering services through EOSC in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 70.

Figure 70: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Offering Services through EOSC

There is a decrease in financial strategies on offering services through EOSC in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Offering Services through EOSC

5.3.2. Progress in Practices on Services

There is no change in national monitoring on offering services through EOSC in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Offering Services through EOSC

There is a decrease in national investments in offering services through EOSC per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 73.

Figure 73: Trend in EU Countries with National Investments in Offering Services through EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

6. Infrastructure

The infrastructure category consists of three main topics: connecting repositories to EOSC, data stewardship, and long-term data preservation.

6.1. Policies

6.1.1. National Policies on Infrastructure

The first main policy question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q25) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q25.1). Connecting repositories to EOSC hereby refers to ensuring that repositories make their research outputs discoverable through EOSC. It remains to be seen how responses to this or a similar question may change in future surveys because of the uptake of the EOSC Federation. 29% (7/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC, whereby 57% (4/7) are mandatory as shown in Figures 74 and 75.

Figure 74: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

Figure 75: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The first main policy question on data stewardship in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on data stewardship?* (Q29) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q29.1). A data steward hereby refers to a professional data steward who supports researchers in their research data management. 46% (11/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on data stewardship, whereby 27% (3/11) are mandatory as shown in Figures 76 and 77.

Figure 76: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

Figure 77: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

The first main policy question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on long-term data preservation?* (Q33) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q33.1). Long-term data preservation hereby refers to ensuring that digital or physical access is provided (taking legitimate interests and constraints into account) to data or other results needed for the validation of the conclusions of peer-reviewed research publications for a substantial period of time (with a minimum of at least 5 years and preferably 10 years) or longer according to disciplinary deposition practices. 33% (8/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on long-term data preservation, whereby 14% (1/7) are mandatory as shown in Figures 78 and 79.

Figure 78: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Long-Term Data Preservation

Figure 79: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Long-Term Data Preservation

6.1.2. Financial Strategies on Infrastructure

The second main policy question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q26). 17% (4/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC as shown in Figures 80 and 81.

Figure 80: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

Figure 81: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The second main policy question on data stewardship in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on data stewardship?* (Q30). 29% (7/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on data stewardship as shown in Figures 82 and 83.

Figure 82: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

Figure 83: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

The second main policy question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation?* (Q34). 17% (4/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation as shown in Figures 84 and 85.

Figure 84: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-Term Data Preservation

Figure 85: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-Term Data Preservation

6.2. Practices

6.2.1. National Monitoring on Infrastructure

The first main practice question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC?* (Q73). 5% (1/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC as shown in Figures 86 and 87.

Figure 86: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

Figure 87: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

The first main practice question on data stewardship in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on data stewardship?* (Q77). 5% (1/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on data stewardship as shown in Figures 88 and 89.

Figure 88: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

Figure 89: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

The first main practice question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation?* (Q81). 5% (1/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation as shown in Figures 90 and 91.

Figure 90: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-Term Data Preservation

Figure 91: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-Term Data Preservation

6.2.2. National Investments in Infrastructure

The second main practice question on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in connecting repositories to EOSC in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q75). 79% (19/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in connecting repositories to EOSC. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 0% (0/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 4% (1/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

The second main practice question on data stewardship in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in data stewardship in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q79). 83% (20/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in

data stewardship. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 8% (2/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 93.

Figure 93: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Data Stewardship per 1000 FTE Researchers

The second main practice question on long-term data preservation in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in long-term data preservation in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q83). 83% (20/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the amount of investments in long-term data preservation. 13% (3/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 94.

Figure 94: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Long-Term Data Preservation per 1000 FTE Researchers

6.3. Impacts

6.3.1. Progress in Policies on Infrastructure

There is an increase in national policies on connecting repositories to EOSC in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is no change in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 95.

Figure 95: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

There is an increase in national policies on data stewardship in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 96.

Figure 96: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Data Stewardship

There is an increase in national policies on long-term data preservation in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is no change in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 97.

Figure 97: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Long-Term Data Preservation

There is a decrease in financial strategies on connecting repositories to EOSC in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 98.

Figure 98: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

There is no change in financial strategies on data stewardship in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 99.

Figure 99: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Data Stewardship

There is no change in financial strategies on long-term data preservation in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 100.

Figure 100: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Long-Term Data Preservation

6.3.2. Progress in Practices on Infrastructure

There is an increase in national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 101.

Figure 101: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Connecting Repositories to EOSC

There is no change in national monitoring on data stewardship in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and overall no change since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 102.

Figure 102: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Data Stewardship

There is a decrease in national monitoring on long-term data preservation in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and overall no change since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 103.

Figure 103: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Long-Term Data Preservation

There is no change in national investments in connecting repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 104.

Figure 104: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Connecting Repositories to EOSC per 1000 FTE Researchers

There is an increase in national investments in data stewardship per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 105.

Figure 105: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Data Stewardship per 1000 FTE Researchers

There is a decrease in national investments in long-term data preservation per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall decrease since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 106.

Figure 106: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Long-Term Data Preservation per 1000 FTE Researchers

7. Skills/Training

The skills/training category consists of one main topic: skills/training for Open Science.

7.1. Policies

7.1.1. National Policy on Skills/Training

The first main policy question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q37) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q37.1). 65% (15/23) of responding EU countries have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science, whereby 7% (1/15) are mandatory as shown in Figures 107 and 108.

Figure 107: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Skills/Training for Open Science

Figure 108: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Skills/Training for Open Science

7.1.2. Financial Strategy on Skills/Training

The second main policy question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q38). 35% (8/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science as shown in Figures 109 and 110.

Figure 109: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/Training for Open Science

Figure 110: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/Training for Open Science

7.2. Practices

7.2.1. National Monitoring on Skills/Training

The first main practice question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science?* (Q85). 17% (4/23) of

responding EU countries have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science as shown in Figures 111 and 112.

Figure 111: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/Training for Open Science

Figure 112: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/Training for Open Science

7.2.2. National Investments in Skills/Training

The second main practice question on skills/training for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in skills/training for Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q87). 75% (18/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in skills/training for Open Science. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 8% (2/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 113.

Figure 113: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Skills/Training for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

7.3. Impacts

7.3.1. Progress in Policies on Skills/Training

There is an increase in national policies on skills/training for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 114.

Figure 114: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Skills/Training for Open Science

There is no change in financial strategies on skills/training for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 115.

Figure 115: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Skills/Training for Open Science

7.3.2. Progress in Practices on Skills/Training

There is no change in national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and overall no change since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 116.

Figure 116: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Skills/Training for Open Science

There is an increase in national investments in skills/training for Open Science per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 117.

Figure 117: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Skills/Training for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

8. Assessment

The assessment category consists of one main topic: incentives/rewards for Open Science.

8.1. Policies

8.1.1. National Policy on Assessment

The first main policy question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q41) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q41.1). 52% (12/23) of responding EU countries have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science, whereby 33% (4/12) are mandatory as shown in Figures 118 and 119.

Figure 118: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

Figure 119: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

8.1.2. Financial Strategy on Assessment

The second main policy question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q42). 30% (7/23) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science as shown in Figures 120 and 121.

Figure 120: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

Figure 121: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

8.2. Practices

8.2.1. National Monitoring on Assessment

The first main practice question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science?* (Q89). 14%

(3/22) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science as shown in Figures 122 and 123.

Figure 122: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

Figure 123: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

8.2.2. National Investments in Assessment

The second main practice question on incentives/rewards for Open Science in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in incentives/rewards for Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q91). 83% (20/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science. 17% (4/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 0% (0/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 124.

Figure 124: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Incentives/Rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

8.3. Impacts

8.3.1. Progress in Policies on Assessment

There is a decrease in national policies on incentives/rewards for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is an increase in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 125.

Figure 125: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

There is an increase in financial strategies on incentives/rewards for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 126.

Figure 126: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

8.3.2. Progress in Practices on Assessment

There is no change in national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 127.

Figure 127: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Incentives/Rewards for Open Science

There is an increase in national investments in incentives/rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall decrease since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 128.

Figure 128: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Incentives/Rewards for Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

9. Engagement

The engagement category consists of one main topic: citizen science.

9.1. Policies

9.1.1. National Policy on Engagement

The first main policy question on citizen science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national policy on citizen science?* (Q45) followed by *Is this policy mandatory?* (Q41.1). 50% (12/24) of responding EU countries have a national policy on citizen science, whereby 17% (2/12) are mandatory as shown in Figures 129 and 130.

Figure 129: Map of EU Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

Figure 130: Share of EU Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

9.1.2. Financial Strategy on Engagement

The second main policy question on citizen science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a financial strategy on citizen science?* (Q46). 17% (4/24) of responding EU countries have a financial strategy on citizen science as shown in Figures 131 and 132.

Figure 131: Map of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

Figure 132: Share of EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

9.2. Practices

9.2.1. National Monitoring on Engagement

The first main practice question on citizen science in Survey 2024 is *Does your country have a national monitoring on citizen science?* (Q93). 13% (3/23) of responding EU countries have a national monitoring on citizen science as shown in Figures 133 and 134.

Figure 133: Map of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

Figure 134: Share of EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

9.2.2. National Investments in Engagement

The second main practice question on citizen science in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in citizen science in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q95). 75% (18/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the number of investments in citizen science. 21% (5/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 4% (1/24) >50 to 100 €K, 0% (0/24) >100 to 250 €K, 0% (0/24) >250 to 500 €K, 0% (0/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 0% (0/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers in citizen science as shown in Figure 135.

Figure 135: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in Citizen Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

9.3. Impacts

9.3.1. Progress in Policies on Engagement

There is no change in national policies on citizen science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022, whereby there is no change in mandatory policies in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 136.

Figure 136: Progress in EU Countries with a National Policy on Citizen Science

There is no change in financial strategies on citizen science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 137.

Figure 137: Progress in EU Countries with a Financial Strategy on Citizen Science

9.3.2. Progress in Practices on Engagement

There is an increase in national monitoring on citizen science in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 138.

Figure 138: Progress in EU Countries with a National Monitoring on Citizen Science

There is an increase in national investments in citizen science per 1000 FTE researchers in EU countries in Survey 2024 from the previous year and an overall increase since Survey 2022 as shown in Figure 139.

Figure 139: Progress in EU Countries with National Investments in Citizen Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

10. Total Investments in EOSC and Open Science

10.1. Total Investments in Millions of Euros

This report has so far looked at national investments across the eight categories relevant for EOSC and Open Science of publications, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills/training, assessment, and engagement. A general question on national investments in Survey 2024 is *How much did your country financially invest in total in EOSC and Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q147). 38% (9/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the total amount of investments in EOSC and Open Science. 4% (1/24) EU countries invested >0 to 1 €M, 25% (6/24) >1 to 5 €M, 0% (0/24) >5 to 10 €M, 25% (6/24) >10 to 50 €M, 8% (2/24) >50 to 100 €M, and 0% (0/24) >100 €M as shown in Figure 140.

Figure 140: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in EOSC and Open Science in Millions of Euros

10.2. Total Investments per 1000 FTE Researchers

The figures reported in Survey 2024 for the general question *How much did your country financially invest in total in EOSC and Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?* (Q147) can be better compared across countries by being relativised to 1000 FTE researchers in the country. 38% (9/24) of responding EU countries are not investing or have not stated the total amount of investments in EOSC and Open Science. 8% (2/24) of EU countries invested >0 to 50 €K, 13% (3/24) >50 to 100 €K, 25% (6/24) >100 to 250 €K, 4% (1/24) >250 to 500 €K, 8% (2/24) >500 to 1000 €K, and 4% (1/24) >1000 €K per 1000 FTE researchers as shown in Figure 141.

Figure 141: Number of EU Countries with National Investments in EOOS and Open Science per 1000 FTE Researchers

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